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ПРОБЛЕМИ ВНУТРІШНЬО ПЕРЕМІЩЕНИХ ОСІБ В КОНТЕКСТІ ЗАБЕЗПЕЧЕННЯ СОЦІАЛЬНОЇ БЕЗПЕКИ В УКРАЇНІ

Шимченко Л.А.

Предметом дослідження є проблеми внутрішньо переміщених осіб в контексті існуючого в Україні «суспільства ризику» та при необхідності забезпечення консолідації українського суспільства в умовах гібридної війни.

Метою статті є: дослідити проблему внутрішньо переміщених осіб в Україні з позицій соціальної безпеки.

Теоретичною та методологічною основою роботи послужили нормативні акти України, друковані періодичні матеріали та інтернет-ресурси.

Результати роботи. Акцентується увага на наявності в Україні ознак «суспільства ризику» і система вирішення проблеми внутрішньо переміщених осіб є тому одним із доказів.

Галузь застосування результатів. Матеріал доцільно застосовувати при проведенні лекційних та семінарських занять з курсів Соціальної економіки, Соціально-економічної безпеки, Національної економіки.

Висновки. Основні зусилля органів влади на всіх рівнях повинні концентруватися на розробці та ефективному впровадженні системи соціально-економічних та культурних змін для швидкої соціальної адаптації внутрішньо переміщених осіб, задоволення їх найбільших потреб через створення нових робочих місць та будівництво повноцінного житла, залучаючи переселенців до суспільного життя територій їх тимчасового перебування.

Ключові слова: внутрішньо переміщені особи, «суспільство ризику», соціальна політика, соціальна безпека, соціалізація, ідентифікація особи, самовизначення громадян.

ПРОБЛЕМЫ ВНУТРЕННЕ ПЕРЕМЕЩЕННЫХ ЛИЦ В КОНТЕКСТЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ СОЦИАЛЬНОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В УКРАИНЕ

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Ключевые слова: внутренне перемещённые лица, «общество риска», социальная политика, социальная безопасность, социализация, идентификация личности, самоопределение граждан.

PROBLEMS OF INTERNALLY DISPLACED PERSONS IN THE CONTEXT OF ENSURING SOCIAL SECURITY IN UKRAINE

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The subject of study is problems of the internally displaced persons in the context of a «risk society» existing in Ukraine and providing consolidation of the Ukrainian society under conditions of the hybrid warfare, if necessary.

The article purpose is to examine a problem of the internally displaced persons in Ukraine from the standpoint of social security.

Theoretical and methodological frameworks of the work encompass legislative acts of Ukraine, print periodicals and Internet resources.

Research results. The author focuses on existence of features of the «risk society» in Ukraine. A system for solving problems of the internally displaced persons is one of evidences of this fact.

Sphere of application of the results. It is expedient to apply the obtained results in holding lectures and workshops in Social Economics, Socio-economic Security and National Economy.

Conclusions. The public authorities at all the levels should concentrate their efforts on development and effective implementation of a system of socio-economic and cultural changes for more rapid social adaptation of the internally displaced persons, meeting their greatest needs through creation of new jobs and construction of permanent housing, involving the displaced persons in the social life of territories, where they temporary stay.

Key words: internally displaced persons, «risk society», social policy, social security, socialization, person identification, self-determination.

Topicality of the research. Considering a state as the main center of social domination aimed at ensuring guarantees and conditions for sustainable public and political development, the durable and stable economic growth, effective control over public funds and gradual expansion of welfare to all segments of a population, the author concludes that the Ukrainian state may be attributed to non-effective or failed states. Avoiding the latter term, the author refers to non-efficiency, particularly emphasizes one very painful aspect – a social policy regarding socially vulnerable categories of the population. There are 1.7 million internally displaced persons and 2.8 million persons with disabilities in Ukraine and 60% of Ukraine's population is living below the poverty line (up to \$1.9 per day), Neal Walker, UNDP Resident Representative in Ukraine, officially said while presenting in June 2017 the UNDP's Human Development Report [1]. Hence, the theme chosen for research is of great importance.

Level of scientific development of the research topic. A considerable number of Ukrainian scholars such as E.M. Libanova, V.N. Novikov, L.M. Cherenko, O.V. Makarova, O.M. Paliy, O.M. Khmelevska, L.P. Duma, Z.V. Medvid, N.P. Boretska, S.I. Pantsyr, T.V. Semyhina, etc. develops a matter of a social policy in own scientific papers. Their researches mainly orient towards examination of theoretical and methodological, methodical and applied issues regarding a system of social protection of the population, the increase of its effectiveness and further enhancement. Scientific papers of U. Beck, N. Luhmann, A. Giddens, C. Lau, as well as O. Yanytskyi, V. Zubkova, S. Yakovleva, V. Ibrahimov, et al. have scientifically contributed to studying an issue of social protection of the population under conditions of the «risk society». However, some theoretical and practical matters, particularly those concerned with new tendencies and innovative processes in the system of social services of Ukraine, especially those related to social security of the internally displaced persons, have not been sufficiently researched.

The article purpose consists in examination of a problem of the internally displaced persons in Ukraine from the standpoint of social security.

Presentation of the main research results. According to the Constitution of Ukraine, the state is a social state guaranteeing a high level of social security and social protection of its citizens. Achieving such level is possible owing to undertaking an effective social policy by particular entities, activity of which is stipulated by the certain social interests and is based on particular legal acts. Such entities encompass public authorities, local self-governance, non-governmental organizations and voluntary organizations. The international law declares that a state, which determines general frameworks, a purpose, goals, priorities, a legislative basis of a social policy and puts the latter into practice, is a major subject of its implementation. The main indices of effectiveness of a state's social policy include a level of welfare, education, population health, social stability, constructiveness of social relations, etc. We will try to ascertain what features are inherent to modern Ukraine in the context of social security.

For the last four years, there have been cardinal breakthroughs in Ukraine: the Revolution of Dignity took place; the European vector of development was enshrined in the government policy; the national economy faced the profound world and civilizational crisis; the state defends own right to existence through diplomatic channels and military means. Temporary occupation of the certain territories and the conduct of anti-terrorism operation considerably affect socio-economic development of the state now. There have been numerous forced relocations in Ukraine since 2014. According to data of social security departments of regional administrations and the Kyiv city State Administration, 1.493,057 million persons or 1.218,611 million families from the Donbas and Crimea were registered as at February 5, 2018 [2].

In September 2017, the European Commission raised the question about distribution of 50,000 refugees from conflict zones of the Middle East and Africa between the EU member countries. Nevertheless, only 16 of the 28 EU member countries proposed to shelter refugees, preparing 34,000 places for them as at mid-November 2017 [3]. According to the world information sources, 65.6 million persons have been forced to leave their homes by the end of 2016. This year alone, about 10.3 million persons left their homes. Within the period 2011-2016, 12 million persons, or approximately 2/3 of a country's population, have migrated from Syria [4].

Such number of relocation of people one way or another demonstrates formation of the «risk society». Let us remind that the German sociologist Ulrich Beck in his scientific paper «Risk Society, Towards a New Modernity» has formulated a term of the «risk society» for the first time. The scientist has linked its sense with security as a normative ideal of the present era. A profound conflict and breakdown within the very society emerges because the industrial society has produced goods as well as a large number of global and extra social risks, which are not always controlled by a human. A majority of social entities ceases to realize and support functional obligations of their activities at the required level. Correspondingly, social consciousness more and more accuses of posing threats such as criminalization of economies and states, ecological problems and deterioration of health of the planet's population, unemployment and poverty, devaluation of family and general social relationships, the increase of irresponsibility in a society or state rather than focuses on achieving a certain level of welfare.

In addition, U. Beck has placed social architecture and political dynamics of civilizational threats to own existence at the heart of his research. The scholar has set out these threats in five theses:

- risks emerging at the highest stage of development of productive forces (in particular, consequences of the influences of toxins and pollutants in foodstuffs, which are beyond our perception...). They induce systematic and often irreversible harm, but generally remain invisible. These risks only exist in terms of (scientific and non-scientific, reliable or unreliable) knowledge about them.

- means of information and means for examination of an extent of a risk become the core social and political positions.

- determination and growth of risks stipulate situations being dangerous for a society. Although risks to some extent demonstrate the social and class structure, they bring different logic into play: «risks of modernization sooner or later also strike those produce or profit from them». Even the rich and powerful are not safe from hazards to health, legitimization, property and profit. Simultaneously, risks produce and expand new global inequalities between underdeveloped and developed countries as well as among the developed countries themselves.

- civilizational risks are big business. They are a bottomless barrel of infinite and self-producible demands. With economic benefits from produced risks, a society faces the hazards and forms the political potential of the risk society.

- in the risk society consciousness determines being. Potential of the risk society must be analyzed from the standpoint of categories of the origin and diffusion of knowledge about risks.

Publicity and governments interfere in spheres previously considered «unpolitical», undertaking a «policy of elimination of causes in the industrialization process itself». There is the public dispute over defining risks. The political potential of catastrophes emerges in the risk society [5, p. 77].

Without going into detail, the author may assert there are all the features of the «risk society» in Ukraine. The system of solving the problem of the internally displaced persons is a clear example of this. The conflict is concerned with tangible goods and the loss of confidence in the future and traditional lifestyle. Circumstances such as the change of human values, military actions and the loss of an enormous number of young lives for a long time against a background of offshore accounts of a part of Ukrainian citizens and increasing wealth of those responsible for stability in the country cause the social and political potential of catastrophes.

A process of formation of various social structures, establishing interrelations, seeking balance in the social environment, delimitation of interests of different socio-political forces occur during the whole period of transformation under military conditions. At the same time, processes of socialization (re-socialization), seeking own identity, self-determination of the citizens, which take the form of a wide range of contradictory and, frequently, radical aspirations occur in the country [6, p. 7].

The author agrees with the widespread view that migrants are a new element of a social environment, which decreases a general level of safety of various groups of a host population and produces different types of risks [7, p. 61]. Current migration needs formation of a managing system that would operate as an independent social institution being able to accomplish new goals through principally new methods. The

legislation of Ukraine does not determine a concept «internal forced migration», but uses a term «internally displaced person» (IDP). In accordance with Article 1 of the Law of Ukraine «On Ensuring of Rights and Freedoms of *Internally Displaced Persons*», an *internally displaced person* is a citizen of Ukraine, foreigner or stateless person lawfully residing in the territory of Ukraine that was forced to leave his place of residence as a result of or in order to avoid negative impact of armed conflict, temporary occupation, widespread violence, violations of human rights and disasters of natural or man-made origin [8, p. 7].

From the point of view of an ordinary citizen, the very definition does not contain an element of state's fault and responsibility for lack of actions on elimination of a source of the problem related to forced replacement. Uniqueness of each person and person's problems has not been taken into account in formulation of types of aid for forcibly displaced persons: one has just driven his BMW from Donetsk to Kyiv and expects for returning home and another has fled bombardments because of a clear threat to the life. Such acceptable forms of solving the problem of forcibly displaced persons (FDPs) have stipulated emergence of a so-called phenomenon «lonely crowd», i.e. loneliness in a crowd, concentration of dispersed persons managed by other persons in qualitatively new and critical circumstances. If the persons remain under a state of such «crowd» for a long-term, their consciousness will change catastrophically. Social catastrophes become one of forms of such inverted consciousness [9, p. 137].

The largest number of the FDP has been deployed in the Kharkiv, Luhansk, Donetsk, Dnipropetrovsk, Zaporizhzhia, Kyiv regions and the city of Kyiv. A total of the internally displaced persons includes more than 771.8 thousand pensioners, 49.8 thousand people with disabilities and 227.4 thousand children. In general, a number of families, who received one-time assistance during January-November 2017, accounts for 1,875,842 families (a monthly average number accounts for 170,531). The government provided financial help amounted to 2.579,9 UAH million as at November 16, 2017 [10].

Not only does the state, but non-governmental organizations, volunteer groups, certain funds and indifferent people deal with problems of the FDPs. Drawing on results of research of the UN Refugee Agency (United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, UNHCR) conducted in February-March 2017, the author indicates problems concerned with discrimination, administrative and bureaucratic impediments to the implementation of their rights, housing problems, absence of prospects for integration in the territory of residence and the deep concern about search for long-term decisions. Many of them feel hopelessness and isolation in spite of years lived in Ukraine. Those, who have gained the refugee status or additional protection, face problems related to opportunities of naturalization and stable living in Ukraine.

Problems of the FDPs and persons facing a threat of displacement comprise high rent, absence of employment prospects, difficulties in receiving state subsidies for compensation of high costs for municipal services and understanding that there are less and less chances to return to a former place of residence in the near future. The FDPs consider administrative and procedural obstacles, absence of the political will, coordination and understanding on the part of governmental officials to be the main reasons of their problems. Many of FDPs suffer discrimination from the Ukrainian society and conclude that governmental officials do not apply sufficient efforts to ensure a FDP full access to own rights [11].

Social and cultural aspects of the forced internal migration are also worth paying especial attention to while examining problems of the FDPs. The internally displaced persons are forced to abandon their traditional usual way of life, rules and ways of behavior and to accept new ones. Such steps frequently result in a cultural shock and psychological trauma. What reasons do cause such consequences? Why is it so important? The author will try to analyze these reasons on level of socio-cultural importance of national identity, where dominating identity gives name to a country (state) and give its life meaning. Dominating identity is referred to as self-identification of a human with a certain society, its values, history, a territory, culture, state and legal institutions, which is a determinative factor of implementation and protection of the internal and external interests of a personality. The main purpose of formation of person's dominating identity is achievement of psychological understanding a unity of destinies of all members of a nation regardless of their ethnic origin, formation of a sense of responsibility for existence and development of a nation, willingness to protect its freedom and independence. The weakness of national identity leads to the increase of a tendency, which is inherent to representatives of ethnical groups compactly settled in some regions of the country, to identify themselves with the people of neighboring countries. Such weakness is an incentive for adjacent states to create scenarios of «protection own citizens» in these territories [12, p. 178].

Triggering the war, Russia used the idea of «protection of own citizens» in the territories of Ukraine. More and more researchers point to a low level of Ukrainian identity in Crimea and the Donbas. There was a time when the state did not take notice of a problem related to prevailing regional identification and a low figure of Ukrainian identity of citizens dragged into the military confrontation in the east of Ukraine and

Crimea. Weakening and «blurring» the Ukrainian identity generate separatism. Hence, pro-Soviet Russian self-identity of inhabitants of the eastern and southern regions as well as denial of striving to European values expressed by a majority of the Ukrainian population have led to a political and socio-economic conflict and fostered support of the Russian Federation's aggression against Ukraine.

The European-oriented Ukrainian identity of a part of citizens from the Donbas and Crimea has become a driving force of mass migration processes in Ukraine. To some extent, such process has fostered emergence of a new type of a «cultural archetype»: self-determination of Ukrainians; uncertainty regarding the future; the distrust of the existing authorities; the search and usage of alternative ways of life support; insuppressibility and recklessness; leaving it up to the fate rather than relying on own self-governing will in relation to lifetime achievements.

Consequently, a socio-cultural phenomenon has become one of key phenomena in the system of forced internal migration. The Ukrainian identity as a basis of the socio-cultural phenomenon is a determinative framework of state-building being able to affirm our national continuity and distinctiveness and, thus, to irreversibly legitimize a fact of existence of the Ukrainian state and nation. The exclusive nature of Ukraine should provide appearance of general Ukrainian senses, meanings, an outlook paradigm and integrity of a cultural environment, i.e. all the components united by a conception of identity. The Ukrainian identity is the determinative background for formation of democratic frameworks underlying the life of the society and national state. Such status for Ukraine is enshrined in documents of the UNO and UNESCO [12, p. 179].

Conclusions. The public authorities at all the levels should concentrate their main efforts on development and effective implementation of a system of socio-economic and cultural changes for more rapid social adaptation of the internally displaced persons, meeting their greatest needs through creation of new jobs and construction of permanent housing, involving the displaced persons in the social life of territories, where they temporary stay.

In the process of rendering various services, governmental officials have to avoid location-dependence and provide access to services at the place of actual residence rather than at the registered place of residence. Moreover, governmental officials should widely disseminate information on opportunities of employment, proposing, if necessary, flexible forms of employment, fly-in fly-out jobs, part-time employment and remote jobs. They should formulate a system of proposals regarding affordable housing for labor migrants on a basis of public-private partnership.

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СПЕЦИФІКА І ЗАКОНОМІРНОСТІ ТРАНСФОРМАЦІЇ АГРАРНИХ ВІДНОСИН В КРАЇНАХ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНО-СХІДНОЇ ЄВРОПИ

Шульга О.А.

Аграрні трансформації в країнах Центрально-Східної Європи мають як спільні риси, так і національні особливості. Вивчення досвіду ринкових реформ в аграрному секторі цих країн має важливе значення для виявлення тенденцій та закономірностей трансформацій аграрних відносин, адже дозволить розробити виважену стратегію та тактику подальших ринкових реформ в аграрному секторі України та повніше врахувати при цьому негативні чинники, які мали місце в умовах трансформаційних процесів у сільському господарстві країн з перехідною економікою.

Предмет дослідження – закономірності та суперечності формування нової системи економічних відносин в аграрному секторі країн з перехідною економікою в результаті його ринкової трансформації. Для з'ясування і розкриття даного питання були застосовані діалектичний та системний підходи, історичний метод, методи аналізу і синтезу, узагальнення та інші. Мета статті – з'ясувати специфіку та закономірності трансформації аграрних відносин в країнах Центрально-Східної Європи, визначити суперечності проведених трансформацій.

Проведення аграрних реформ у країнах з перехідною економікою Центрально-Східної Європи можна умовно поділити на три періоди: на першому етапі – стратегічним завданням була структурна реформа аграрного сектора, в основі якої лежала приватизація землі; на другому етапі відбулася радикальна зміна напрямку внутрішньої аграрної політики в напрямку політики підтримки цін і ринків, експортних і імпорتنих обмежень; на третьому етапі відбувалася (а в деяких країнах вже відбулася) підготовка до вступу в ЄС. Ціллю аграрних реформ в країнах Центрально-Східної Європи було перетворення аграрного сектору їх національних економік на ринково орієнтований сектор економіки. Для досягнення цієї цілі були поставлені такі завдання: приватизація землі і реорганізація колишніх сільськогосподарських підприємств, структурна перебудова аграрного сектору; лібералізація ринків, проведення